

The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Teacher's Organizational Commitment Based on (Louis W. Fry Model): A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to investigate the influence of principal's spiritual leadership on teacher's organizational commitment. Spiritual leadership is very interesting to study, because this leadership concept is a synthesis of value-based leadership constructs to answer problems related to human relations. Spiritual leadership has an important role to play in education as it can help build good relationships between principals and teachers, and increase teachers' emotional and psychological attachment to the organization. Spiritual leadership can also help improve the quality of education and organizational performance. In addition, spiritual leadership can help improve teacher retention issues and increase organizational commitment. By applying spiritual leadership, principals can motivate and inspire individuals and engage every member of the organization to achieve school goals. Therefore, spiritual leadership can help create a positive learning environment and build a strong organizational culture in schools. The method used in this study was a literature review to investigate the influence of principals' spiritual leadership on teachers' organizational commitment. The article selection procedure was very rigorous using various selected journal databases to select ten research articles that met the inclusive criteria of this study. The results of this study show that spiritual leadership of school principals can significantly influence teachers' organizational commitment.

KEYWORDS: Influence, Literature Review, Spiritual Leadership, Teacher Organizational Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Background of this article

Leadership style is one of the most important success factors in an organization and the type of leadership is a unique behavior of a leader in leading, motivating, guiding and managing a group of people in an organization [1]. School is a complex organization, where in this complex organization there are many dynamics in all aspects that occur in this educational institution. As an organization with a high level of complexity, it requires a leader who is able to coordinate this organization maturely [2]. In managing the educational organization, the role of the principal becomes very important to support the performance of an organization and the success of the school depends on how the principal leads, therefore the principal is a vital organ in the school ecosystem [3]. Principals must understand what kind of leadership model or approach should be applied and adapted to the current state of development, especially its implementation in an educator or teacher because the success and failure of the school is caused by those who lead the school and the teachers in it [4]. In this modern era, leaders are not only focused on every learning process [5]. The principal should be able to create a positive and productive work environment in the school with personality values that can be emulated by the teachers from the principal [6]. One of the leadership models that can be applied is spiritual leadership.

Spiritual leadership is a human-centered and value-oriented leadership theory in which leaders intrinsically motivate their followers and themselves. Spiritual leadership is considered a synthesis of the constructs of servant leadership, principle-centered, charismatic leadership, and transformational leadership. The theory emerged in the late 1990s and early 2000s as a response to the lack of job security and various other factors [7]. The form of spiritual leadership is able to influence a person or group to want to cooperate, commit and be loyal to carry out all activities in accordance with their duties and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals in improving quality and performance through the three spiritual aspects of the Louis W. Fry Model, namely visions, hope/faith, and altruistic love which will further encourage organizational commitment [8]. Organizational commitment is the level of a person's desire to remain in an organization and actively participate in achieving organizational goals [9]. Principals must be able to apply spiritual leadership to their teachers, because teachers are an important part of organizing education. Teachers will find it difficult to carry out their roles and responsibilities as educators if they do not have a commitment to spiritual leadership [10] cause the spirit

in spiritual leadership can bind everyone in the organization and encourage not only unity and care, but also productivity and reduce teachers turnover [11]. Based on the background that has been described, this literature review contributes to adding and developing existing literature to provide more understanding regarding the influence of the principal's spiritual leadership on teacher organizational commitment.

Gap of Literature Review

Many theories suggest different leadership styles. In this study, the author focuses on spiritual leadership. The concept of spiritual leadership is a leadership approach that focuses on spiritual and moral values in leading an organization or team. Spiritual leadership emphasizes the importance of integrity, honesty, empathy and caring for others. In an organizational context, spiritual leadership can help increase employee engagement and commitment, and create a harmonious and productive work environment. So through this journal review, I will examine in more depth spiritual leadership implemented in educational institutions (schools), to add to the development of new theories about spiritual leadership in schools, because so far the same research has only focused on companies, courses, government, shops, and hospitals, but there is still very little research in schools. This is an important point and interest for author to conduct research or study further.

METHOD

The method used in the preparation of this article is a literature review as a foundation. This literature review is carried out to analyze, critically review, synthesize, summarize and compare the results of research obtained from certain sources related to relevant topics on the object under study to reconstruct a research result and help researchers understand more about research topics in accordance with a good and correct scientific framework [12]. This literature review is focused on Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Commitment within the scope of educational institutions (schools). The review process is drawn from relevant literature using transparent and reproducible search methods and the data obtained can be analyzed and synthesized.

The review process begins by using the Google Scholar search engine, to search for international and national articles with keywords: "Principal Spiritual Leadership on Teacher Organizational Commitment", which refers to the theory developed by Louis W. Fry. and identified a total of 155 studies and articles related of this theme. and sorted based on predetermined criteria resulting in 10 articles that will be analyzed further. The criteria for articles in this study are as follows:

1. The research related to spiritual leadership (Louis W. Fry) and organizational commitment.
2. The research related to Principal Spiritual Leadership and Teacher Commitment conducted at school.
3. The research articles to the last six years 2018 – 2023.
4. National and International articles.
5. Qualitative, Quantitative, Mix Method and Literature Review articles

Furthermore, the articles are analyzed and arranged systematically in one proposition so that they are interrelated so as to produce informative articles and can be used as a source for finding the next research gap regarding "Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Commitment".

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. *Spiritual Leadership Literature Based on Louis W. Fry Model*

The literature review in this section has reported that the spiritual leadership model has potential as a new paradigm in leadership practice. The spiritual leadership model was first proposed by Fry in 2003. Fry's 2003 model contributes to integrating three spiritual aspects (vision, hope/faith and altruistic love) in a leader to illustrate how spiritual leadership can be used to improve leader quality and organizational profitability [13] and the form of spiritual leadership is being able to coordinate the comfort and clarity of its followers at work through the three aspects of spiritual leadership. Vision is important in directing and motivating organizational members. Hope/faith is the certainty of things that are expected to be certain that the vision, goals and mission of the organization will be fulfilled. Altruistic love in spiritual leadership is a sense of wholeness, harmony and well-being generated through a leader's care, concern and appreciation for self and others [8].

2. *The Influence of Principal's Spiritual Leadership on Teacher Commitment Organization*

Most of the results of the literature review conducted show the influence of spiritual leadership on organizational commitment.

The research conducted by highlighted [14] the influence of spiritual leadership in attending to the spiritual needs of employees and its positive impact on organizational commitment. The results show that spiritual leadership has a positive relationship with organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is considered important because it can affect performance, job satisfaction, and employee retention in the organization. So, three spiritual leadership aspects (vision, hope or faith, and altruistic love) motivates followers to survive through vocation and membership [15]. This is in line with the results of research conducted by [16] which examines employee organizational commitment in South Korea with significant results on the three aspect of spiritual leadership from Fry (2003). So, the reaserach of [17] has reported that Islamic university leaders and administrators in Malang city should focus on spiritual leadership to instill and sustain organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour among university lecturers. This shows that with spiritual leadership in an organization or educational institution, both teachers and education personnel will feel meaning in their work and can help create an inclusive work environment and provide a strong sense of community among organizational members and it can be applied for all principals in Indonesia [18]. In contrast to the findings of research conducted by [3] Based on spiritual leadership theory, vision in a leader is very important in addition to hope/faith and altruistic love. The findings of this study provide something different that the effect of the principal's vision is not very significant on the affective commitment of teachers, this shows that leaders who apply these aspects of spiritual leadership can influence their subordinates in various forms and results. Therefore, this study adds a significant contribution. While hope/faith and altruistic love showed significant results on teachers' affective commitment.

Another study from [19] also examined the teacher's Psychological Capital which mediates the relationship between the principal's spiritual leadership and the teacher's Organizational Commitment. This article examines the relationship between principals' spiritual leadership as perceived by teachers and organizational commitment in Hong Kong schools. The study found that membership and meaning/calling play a mediating role between spiritual leadership and organizational outcomes. The more teachers perceive spiritual behaviors from their principals, the more likely they are to be committed to the school. In particular, the adoption of spiritual leadership can also promote team spirit, inspire devotion, and build good working relationships increasing resilience and empowerment, further enhancing their sense of loyalty and adherence to their school. Also [9] was conducted on a sample of teachers in a high school in Taiwan. The results of this study show that the principal's spiritual leadership has a positive impact on teachers' psychological capital in the school environment, which in turn increases their organizational commitment. [20] also reported some potential challenges in applying spiritual leadership, which can negatively affect organizational commitment. A challenge in implementing spiritual leadership in this article is the possibility of teacher exploitation by principals who have ultra-legitimacy, such as forcing teachers to work beyond the prescribed time limit. Another challenge is an exclusionary environment where the school recognizes only one religious belief, so individuals within the environment cannot express their different beliefs. This can lead to discrimination against students and affect their learning outcomes. Therefore, there needs to be an effort to overcome these challenges and involve the whole school community in the implementation of spiritual leadership.

CONCLUSION

Based on literature review that has been compiled by the author, in general, the spiritual leadership of school principals has a positive influence on teacher commitment. Each aspect of Fry's spiritual leadership such as (Vision, hope/faith and altruistic love) applied by the principal will help create a positive and productive work environment in the school, job satisfaction, strong membership and improve the quality of education provided by teachers to their students. The more teachers perceive spiritual behaviors from the principal, the more likely they are to increase their sense of commitment to the school and this can reduce teacher turnover. The limitation found in this literature review is that article reviews are only in Indonesian and English so other research is not reviewed due to the author's limitations, so there is no single measure that can be compared between studies. The scope of the discussion in this article is still very limited in explaining the influence of the principal's spiritual leadership on teacher commitment, so further research is needed, especially its implementation in educational institutions.

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